

Infrastructure as a shared responsibility: towards an ORI commons

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23 June 2026

AMBITION

“Transform the closed research information infrastructure to an ORI commons”

Open Research
Information
Community Meetup

Februari 9th, 2026
Saxion University of Applied Sciences

INTRODUCTION
Eileen Waegemaekers (SURF)

"IT'S A VERY RICH AND FRAGMENTED LANDSCAPE..."

"THE COMMONS APPROACH"

What we need:

1. COMMON LANGUAGE
2. WORKFLOW PERSPECTIVE
3. FEDERATION
4. SHARED SERVICES

What are the needs?
End-to-end workflow

Data should live locally,
but come together
in a common place

We have the same needs...
Share solutions and services!

THE TRAGEDY OF THE COMMONS:
People overuse it...

Like "common land"
in earlier times...

shared resources
(f.i. wood)

data lake

HOW TO DEAL
with legal and
security rules?

LEGAL
SECURITY

Research Information
is locked in silos...

Everyone comes from
different directions...

ROLES AND
RESPONSIBILITIES
have to be clear!

CALL TO ACTION:
- Who does what?
- Who maintains what?

| Transition

Infrastructure vision for an ORI Commons

OBJECTIVE

**Transform the closed
research information
infrastructure to an ORI
commons**

COLLECTIVE ACTION

We need:

- 1. Clarity on who does what**
- 2. Agreement on who maintains what**
- 3. Commitment to collective value over local optimization**

